

**ON THE ISSUE OF PREVENTION OF GESTATIONAL DIABETES
MELLITUS**

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Annotation

Gestational diabetes mellitus is currently defined as a disease characterized by hyperglycemia, first detected during pregnancy. Hyperglycemia is one of the most common conditions that women face during pregnancy. The diet must be based on the list of permitted foods. A well-chosen diet and sufficient physical activity help prevent the development of complications of gestational diabetes mellitus.

Key words: gestational diabetes mellitus, hyperglycemia, obesity, prevention.

Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is a disease characterized by hyperglycemia (increased blood glucose levels), which was first identified during pregnancy. Most often, a woman's glycemia normalizes after childbirth, but there remains a high risk of developing diabetes mellitus in subsequent pregnancies and in the future.

GDM during pregnancy is a fairly common disease in the world in general. The incidence of hyperglycemia during pregnancy, according to international studies, is up to 18%.

Obesity is an important health problem in many countries. Obesity is currently considered as a multifactorial, chronic, relapsing disease associated with the development of a number of diseases that reduce a person's life expectancy and reduce its quality. Disorders of carbohydrate metabolism can develop in any pregnant woman, taking into account the hormonal and metabolic changes that consistently occur at different stages of pregnancy. But the highest risk of developing gestational diabetes is in pregnant women with: overweight/obesity and age over 25 years; the presence of diabetes in close relatives; disorders of carbohydrate metabolism identified before the current pregnancy (impaired glucose tolerance, impaired fasting glycemia, gestational diabetes in previous pregnancies; birth of a child weighing more than 4000 g).

At the birth of children with diabetic fetopathy, the following are more common: macrosomia (newborn weight ≥ 4000 g, or ≥ 90 th percentile in preterm pregnancy); violation of adaptation to extrauterine life, which is manifested by the immaturity of the newborn even with a full-term pregnancy and its large size; respiratory disorders; asphyxia; hypoglycemia of the newborn; organomegaly (enlarged spleen, liver, heart, pancreas); cardiomyopathy (primary damage to the heart muscle); jaundice; disturbances in the blood coagulation system, the content of erythrocytes (red blood cells) in the blood increases; metabolic disorders (low blood glucose, calcium, potassium, magnesium values).

In children born to mothers with undiagnosed, uncompensated gestational diabetes mellitus, the following are more common: neurological diseases (cerebral palsy, epilepsy) due to birth trauma; during puberty and beyond, the risk of developing obesity, metabolic disorders (in particular carbohydrate metabolism), and cardiovascular diseases is increased.

On the part of a pregnant woman with gestational diabetes mellitus, the following are more common: polyhydramnios; urinary system infections; toxicosis of the second half of pregnancy (a pathological condition that develops in the second half of pregnancy and is manifested by the appearance of edema and increased blood pressure) etc.

GDM does not have any clinical manifestations associated with hyperglycemia (dry mouth, thirst, increased volume of urine excreted per day, itching, etc.), and therefore active detection of this disease is required in all pregnant women.

Conclusion. Prevention of diseases associated with pathology in women, proper nutrition helps prevent GDM in pregnant women

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